

Knowledge and Use of Social Media Platforms for Marketing among Pepper Farmers in Semi-urban Areas in Benue State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Objective: The general objective of this research was to determine the knowledge and use of social media platforms for marketing among pepper farmers in semi-urban areas of Benue State, Nigeria.

Methods: the study made use of descriptive-survey design to elicit data from target respondents. The sample size was 344 pepper farmers in semi-urban areas in Benue state. Data were collected with the use of structured questionnaire, and the results were analysed using percentages, mean and standard deviation.

Result: Many pepper farmers in semi-urban areas in Benue State were aware of social media platforms and have attempted to use one social media platform or the other. Facebook and WhatsApp were the major social media platforms used for marketing among pepper farmers in the area. Findings also revealed that cost-effectiveness, customer relationship, relationship with other pepper farmers, creating awareness, connecting with suppliers of farm inputs, and ability to create wider market were the benefits accrued to pepper farmers for using social media platforms in marketing. The challenges associated with using social media platforms for marketing among pepper farmers in semi-urban areas included constraints to effectively engage in farming, connection issues, compromising farmers' privacy, lack of skills to use social media platforms and continuous negative comments which may discourage sales.

Conclusion: Marketing among pepper farmers has been greatly enhanced since farmers can now utilise social media platforms to conduct marketing activities.

Keywords: knowledge; social media; marketing; pepper farmers; semi-urban.

Introduction

The emergence of the Social Media (SM) platform has created new avenues for marketing farm produce globally. It is convenient to state that social media provides the greatest marketing opportunity compared to any other marketing platform. According to Adejo and Opeyemi (2019), social media is an internet-oriented digital tool for disseminating and discussing information among individuals. It involves information and multimedia that the user generates, disseminates and discusses through digital platforms. Small-scale farmers mostly utilise common social media platforms such as Facebook, X (formerly known as Twitter), WhatsApp, Instagram, LinkedIn, and YouTube to

communicate with the general public about their farm produce. According to Umoru (2024), social media platforms have brought about a new pattern of communication and interaction among people in the marketing world as they provide new opportunities for buying, selling and advertising farming products, thereby raising the visibility and accessibility of products to farmers. Furthermore, through social media platforms, farmers can reach a broader audience and still effectively improve the strategy of selling their farm products.

In sub-Saharan Africa, with a low level of technology among farmers, awareness of SM platforms is critical to marketing farm produce, because for any marketing activity to be very effective in the contemporary digital-driven society, it is important to use the SM in order to reach a wide network of people. This usage is highly limited due to lack of knowledge and awareness of SM platforms among peasant farmers. Atmaje, et al. (2021) opined that the farmers' knowledge regarding marketing agricultural products, especially vegetables, is considered to be low, leading to poor sales and practices. This is largely attributed to a lack of knowledge on the use of SM platforms on pepper farming and marketing practices. It is important to note that several other factors affect the level of awareness and knowledge base regarding the use of SM platforms among farmers in semi-urban areas in Nigeria. The level of education and network coverage availability are significant determinants of awareness of SM platforms among these farmers. Level of income and exposure to media platforms are important variables in farmers' marketing of farming produce. In a study conducted in Bangka Selatan, Indonesia, Atmaja et al (2021) affirms this when they found that the majority of Muntok pepper farmers were primary school farmers and as such, had a low level of awareness and utilisation of SM platforms in marketing their pepper after harvest. The argument here is that the level of education is a greater determinant of whether or not a farmer will be aware and also utilise SM platforms for marketing their farm produce.

In addition, the type of SM platform a farmer uses is crucial in facilitating the marketing of farm produce. Various SM platforms including X (Twitter), TikTok, Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, Telegram, YouTube, LinkedIn, among others are available for farmers to market their farm produce in Nigeria. Ogunsola et al (2022) affirms that Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, LinkedIn, WhatsApp, and other SM platforms are major SM platforms used by farmers for sharing information on marketing farming products and farming economy in today's society, the use of SM in agriculture marketing is seriously gaining attention among farmers. However, the farmer must bear this in mind that the choice of SM platform is to a greater extent dependent on their versatility with the platform and the number of prospective buyers present on the platform.

According to Singh et al (2019), SM platforms connect people with similar interests and transcend geographic borders. Farmers subscribe to SM platforms and traditional media to so for information. Also, numerous blogs discussed agricultural subjects, which can best be explained by the theory of uses and gratification, which explains why people select a particular media to meet their marketing needs. Ramavhale et al (2024) asserts that SM platforms like Facebook, Telegram, TikTok, WhatsApp, and Twitter are used by small-scale farmers for the purpose of marketing. They often use these platforms to unite with

other farmers and communicate with friends and coworkers in order to be informed on current market trends for farming products. Through these platforms, farmers can thus communicate with their customers. Additionally, they have made farmers more visible and active on SM platforms, becoming abreast with modern technology and its relevance in agriculture. In addition to getting information and contacting extension agents, farmers make visuals about their farming operations on SM sites like YouTube. Thus, the greater the number of farmers who share information on the SM platforms, the more prospective buyers it reaches.

In the marketing of perishable farm produce such as pepper, SM's advantages supersede its drawbacks (Ramavhale et al, 2024). Furthermore, a pepper farmer's inability to use the SM platform is a huge disadvantage since it will be difficult for such a farmer to grow. In addition to farmers, agricultural extension agents use SM on their electronic devices to obtain information from farmers when the need arises. Extension officers can adhere to the proper protocols for formalising SM use in their workplaces, including planning, security, marketing, and establishing online communities, because they already use SM daily. Pepper farmers and other small-holder farmers employ metrics such as posts, likes, the number of friends, followers, mentions, and fans on SM platforms to market their products (Ramavhale et al, 2024). Even though SM is relevant for extension officers, they may face difficulties because of their incapacity to conduct practical experiments with farmers, their acceptance of SM, and the fact that traditional extensionists have not embraced it. Also, there are concerns about privacy, cyberbullying, addiction, false information, legal issues, and security.

In Nigeria, there are perceived advantages associated with the knowledge and utilisation of SM platforms in buying and selling farming products in the society. Buying and selling of farm products, especially perishable ones like vegetables, fruits, dairy products, roots and tubers among others, saves the farmers the transportation cost that would have been incurred in transporting the products to the market. According to Esabu et al, (2024), SM platforms are capable of closing the information gap and propel the sharing of vital and timely messages to farmers. The provision of access to agricultural knowledge training materials, and market opportunities that were hitherto not accessible can be fully accessed through these platforms. This connection can enable farmers to have access to experts in the field of agriculture and thereafter, share experiences and provide solutions to nagging problems relating to the marketing of farm produce. For instance, through Facebook advertisement, a farmer in the suburb of an urban area can sell all his/her perishable farm produce cultivated on the same day. This can be achieved with different buyers who are affiliated with the farmer on the platform having simultaneous interest in the products. However, Esabu et al (2021) argue that challenges such as poor internet connectivity and access to digital devices in semi-urban areas, differences in language time barrier, and inadequate availability of specific content that designed for the specific needs of various farmers in semi-urban and rural areas prevents the full usage of SM platforms in agro-communication in Nigeria.

Benue state, an agrarian geographical area, located in North central Nigeria, is endowed with fertile land for growing of varying crops including vegetables with are

largely grown by the bank of river Benue. There are a number of semi-urban areas in the state, including Naka, Udei, Gbajimba, Ihugh, Vandeikya, Wanunne, Adoka, Otukpa, Oju, Awajir, Adikpo, among others, where farmers are found in large numbers. There is need to explore the knowledge and use of SM platforms in marketing among the farmers in the state. SM platforms are of great importance to farmers in urban areas according to studies by Edeghon and Esene (2018), Ogunsola et al (2022), Alabi and Nnaji (2021) and Nwaizugbo and Abereola (2021). However, insufficient empirical evidence proves the knowledge and use of social platforms in semi-urban areas in Benue state, Nigeria. As such, the present study is aimed at empirically investigating the phenomenon, to help pepper farmers in the semi-urban area in the state to become aware and utilise the SM platforms for the purpose of marketing pepper in the contemporary digital media-driven society.

Objectives of the study

The general objective of this study was to determine the knowledge and use of SM platforms for marketing among pepper farmers in semi-urban areas of Benue State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to:

- i. Ascertain the level of awareness of SM platforms for marketing among pepper farmers in semi-urban areas.
- ii. Determine the various SM platforms for marketing among pepper farmers in semi-urban areas.
- iii. Identify the perceived benefits of using SM platforms for marketing among pepper farmers in semi-urban areas.
- iv. Determine the challenges of using SM platforms for marketing among pepper farmers in semi-urban areas.

Methods

The methods that were used in this study are discussed under the following subheadings:

Design of the study: The study used the descriptive-survey design to elicit data from target respondents in the study area. Descriptive-survey design was chosen because it allows a researcher to gather a wide range of information on a given topic of interest. Thus, by adopting the descriptive survey design, pepper farmers can assess the current knowledge and use of SM platforms for marketing pepper farmers in semi-urban areas. This knowledge can be insightful in finding out areas for improvement and providing valuable suggestions for interventions.

Population of the study: This study's target population was pepper farmers who were residents of semi-urban areas in Benue state who engaged in pepper farming for commercial purposes. The farmers must have grown pepper in a quantity enough to sell to the general public. However, since there is no verifiable data on the number of farmers who fall into this category, we consider our population to be infinite.

Sample size/Sampling technique: The sample size for this study was 344 pepper farmers in semi-urban areas in Benue state. The researcher arrived at the sample size after conducting a house-to-house visit in identified semi-urban areas where pepper farmers who

cultivated in commercial quantities were found. Nine (9) semi-urban areas were selected from Benue state, three (3) each from the three geo-political zones in the state. These were Benue North-West, Benue North-East and Benue South Districts. In Benue North-West, Wanunne, Apir and Gbajimba were selected, in Benue North-East, Awajir, Adikpo and Zaki-biam were selected while in Benue South Districts, Okpoga, Otukpa and Oju were selected. The sampling technique was based on snowballing. The process began by identifying a commercial pepper farmer with the assistance of the residents in selected semi-urban areas in the state. After that, the researcher asked the respondent to identify one or more commercial pepper farmers. The researcher snowballed from one commercial pepper farmer to the other in the study area until the required sample size of 344 participants was obtained.

Instrument/validation and reliability: The study utilised a structured questionnaire to collect data from respondents. This instrument was chosen because it is clear and requires less respondent interpretation. The instrument elicited socio-demographic data as well as data related to knowledge and use of SM platforms for marketing among pepper farmers. It was divided into sections A and B, respectively. Questions on socio-demographic variables had multiple options and those related to knowledge and use of SM platforms for marketing among pepper farmers were measured on a four-point Likert Scale. A face-to-face validation of the structured questionnaire developed by the researcher was subjected to validation by the three experts in the field of agriculture and digital marketing research. They assessed both the language and technicalities of the questionnaire to ensure that items measure what they were expected to measure in line with the set objectives of the study. Test-retest reliability was used for the study. Test-retest is chosen because a farmer's utilisation of SM platforms for marketing purposes is expected to be stable over a particular period. Therefore, one would expect an increased result in test-retest reliability coefficient.

Data collection and analysis: This study collected data through face-to-face interaction with participants. Data were collected from 4 pm to 6 pm daily for two weeks. After completion, the participants' responses were sorted out and coded for analysis. The statistical tools employed for the analysis were percentages, mean, and standard deviation, which were done with the aid of statistical software.

Results/Discussion

Out of the 344 questionnaire copies issued to participants, 19 were not completed and thus, were not considered. This implies that 325 questionnaires, constituting 94% return rate, were considered adequate for data analysis. From the sample, 33% were males and 67% were females, indicating that more females engaged in pepper farming in the area. Furthermore, 53% of the participants cultivated more than 3 hectares of land for pepper plantation in a year, suggesting that most participants cultivated pepper in a large quantity for commercial purpose. The mean age of the participants was 38 years. Based on annual income, most participants earned between N1,000,000 to N5,000,000 per annum. Also, 69% of participants were literate as they had at least a primary education. The result of the study is further presented based on the objectives of the study as shown below:

Table 1: Awareness of SM platforms for marketing among pepper farmers

S/N	Items	Mean	Std.Deviation	Decision
1	Many pepper farmers are actively using SM platforms	3.12	.76	Accepted
2	Some pepper farmers are aware of SM platforms	3.63	.67	Accepted
3	A few pepper farmers are skeptical about the use of SM platforms	3.55	.72	Accepted
4	A small number of pepper farmers have not attempted using any	1.31	.59	Rejected
5	Some pepper farmers are engaging with agricultural organisations on SM platforms	3.06	.57	Accepted
6	I have successfully used SM platforms to advertise my products.	3.56	.77	Rejected

The result in Table 1 showed the awareness of SM platforms for marketing among pepper farmers in the study area. The result of the study revealed that five out of the six items raised were accepted as that there is awareness of SM platforms for marketing among pepper farmers. However, the participants rejected the item on a small number of pepper farmers not attempting to use any of the SM platforms. This means that many pepper farmers in semi-urban areas in Benue State have attempted to use one SM platform or the other. This result extended the study of Nwaizugbo and Abereola. (2021), who examined the use of SM in the marketing of agricultural products and farmers' turnover without looking at the awareness of SM platforms for marketing among pepper farmers. Therefore, the current study completed the awareness area and also investigated the use of SM platforms for marketing among pepper farmers.

Table 2: Various SM platforms for marketing among pepper farmers

S/N	Items	Mean	Std.Deviation	Remark
1	I use Facebook to connect with other farmers	3.46	.83	Accepted
2	WhatsApp is becoming popular among us pepper farmers	3.08	.60	Accepted
3	I use Twitter to share real-time updates	1.54	.92	Rejected
4	I use YouTube to sell my pepper	1.33	.81	Rejected
5	TikTok is my major SM platform for making sales	1.49	.96	Rejected
6	LinkedIn is gaining popularity	1.48	.85	Rejected
7	I use Instagram	1.83	1.05	Rejected

Table 2 presents the various SM platforms for marketing pepper in the study area. Only two means were above the accepted point of 2.5 and were therefore accepted. The respondents rejected the use of Twitter, YouTube, TikTok, LinkedIn and Instagram as SM

platforms for marketing pepper in the study area. Thus, Facebook and WhatsApp were the major SM platforms used for marketing among pepper farmers in the area. This study conforms with the study of Ogunsola, et al. (2022) who examined the use of SM for marketing of agricultural commodities in selected markets and found that Facebook was the most preferred SM platform used for marketing among farmers because it was considered more convenient and more popular among the marketers, who were farmers. This information is useful because it could guide farmers on the best SM platform to choose when making similar choices.

Table 3: Perceived benefits of using SM platforms for marketing among pepper farmers

S/N	Items	Mean	Std.Deviation	Remark
1	SM platform is cost-effective	3.56	.70	Accepted
2	It builds relationships with customers	3.48	.78	Accepted
3	It is important tool for receiving feedback	2.04	1.18	Rejected
4	It is relevant in building a relationship with other pepper farmers	3.52	.72	Accepted
5	It assists me to create awareness about the important marketing	3.53	.74	Accepted
6	I use SM platforms to connect with suppliers of farm inputs	3.34	.86	Accepted
7	It is an avenue to reach a wide market easily	3.56	.74	Accepted

Inference is made from Table 3 of the perceived benefits of using SM platforms for marketing among pepper farmers in semi-urban areas of Benue State. The result shows that the participant accepted six of the seven items raised. However, the statement on SM platforms constituting an essential tool for receiving feedback was rejected. This implies that SM platforms benefit pepper farmers in terms of marketing. This result is in line with an extant study by Karle and Mishra (2022), who observed that SM platforms assist farmers with building quick relationships, raising awareness, creating economic opportunities, and increasing access to resources and knowledge. The uniqueness of this study is that it focused more on pepper farmers and not just farmers and agriculture in general.

Table 1: Challenges of using SM platforms for marketing among farmers

S/N	Items	Mean	Std.Deviation	Decision
1	Use of SM platform may constrain pepper farmers from effectively engaging in farming	3.52	.78	Accepted
2	It poses connection issues	3.69	.55	Accepted
3	It has the ability to compromise the farmers' privacy	3.16	.56	Accepted
4	Farmers may lack the skills to use SM platform	3.49	.80	Accepted
5	The constantly changing algorithms and trends on SM platforms can be overwhelming for pepper farmers.	2.23	.98	Rejected

6 Managing negative comments on SM platforms can be challenging 3.50 .82 Accepted

In Table 4, the researcher identified the challenges of using SM platforms for marketing among pepper farmers in semi-urban areas of Benue State. Five out of the six items were accepted as challenges to pepper farmers. The item which states that the constantly changing algorithms and trends on SM platforms can be overwhelming for pepper farmers was rejected. Implicitly, the result suggests that the use of SM platforms for marketing has some challenges. This result has confirmed the study of Gever et al. (2023), who observed that, aside from the farmers' experiences of not having enough access to the internet in the use of different SM platforms, connectivity is another problem with the utilisation of the SM for marketing purposes. This result could be useful to farmers when deciding on the use of SM platforms for marketing products.

Conclusion/Recommendations

From the findings of the study, it can be concluded that marketing among pepper farmers has been greatly enhanced since farmers can now utilise social media platforms to conduct marketing activities. However, the use of social media platforms like TikTok, Instagram, Telegram, YouTube, LinkedIn, and X is not popular among farmers as it has certain disadvantages. It is therefore recommended that:

- i. Farmers who have increased the marketing of their pepper through social media platforms can also sensitise other farmers to use social media platforms to market their produce.
- ii. Farmers should be encouraged to use other social media platforms than Facebook and WhatsApp through their associations, as is the case in the study area.
- iii. Agricultural extension workers should educate farmers on the efficient ways to use social media platforms in marketing
- iv. Finally, further research should be conducted to examine the effects of social media platforms on modern farming techniques in Benue State, Nigeria.

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